

RESEARCH ARTICLE

English language proficiency, perception and competence among the academic staff of public universities in Kosovo

[version 1; peer review: 2 approved with reservations]

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Abstract

Background

English language proficiency is increasingly vital for higher education institutions due to globalization and the internationalization of academic programs. In Kosovo, public universities are experiencing similar pressures to adopt English as a medium of communication and instruction.

Methods

This study investigates how academic staff perceive their English language proficiency and its influence on their academic responsibilities and institutional roles. A mixed-method case study was conducted involving 336 academic staff members from all public universities in Kosovo. Data were collected through an online questionnaire distributed via email between October and December 2024. The survey included both closed- and open-ended questions assessing self-perceived language proficiency, usage in professional contexts, and attitudes toward English in higher education.

Results

Revealed that most lecturers rated their English proficiency as "good" or "very good," and a majority acknowledged the importance of English for academic work, publication, and international collaboration. While English was not a formal job requirement for many, respondents agreed it facilitated research, access to academic resources, and professional networking. Key challenges included lack of formal training and limited institutional support. Open-ended

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responses emphasized the role of English in improving academic quality, access to international literature, and communication with foreign colleagues. English language proficiency plays a crucial role in the academic and professional development of university staff in Kosovo. Despite institutional gaps in formal language policies, the increasing demand for English in research, teaching, and international engagement signals the need for strategic support in language development.

Conclusion

In this study highlights the urgency of aligning institutional goals with language competence to ensure quality and competitiveness in the global academic arena.

Plain Language Summary

This study examines the academic, linguistic, and personal development of English Language students from the University “Ukshin Hoti” in Prizren who participated in study abroad programs. A mixed-method approach, including questionnaires and interviews, was used to analyze the experiences of 30 participants who studied in countries such as Germany, England, Turkey, and the USA. The findings reveal that studying abroad significantly enhances language proficiency, with 80% reporting improved oral fluency, 76.7% better pronunciation, and 70% expanded vocabulary.

Students identified cultural differences as both challenges and opportunities for growth, particularly in socialization and classroom communication styles. Personal motivations included gaining independence and engaging with new communities, while academic goals focused on achieving bilingual competence and improving employability. Most participants credited their study abroad experience with fostering critical thinking, time management, and intercultural communication skills.

The study concludes that immersion in a target language environment is transformative, providing students with lifelong benefits in language acquisition, career prospects, and global awareness. However, it also highlights the need for careful preparation to address cultural adaptation challenges and maximize the benefits of studying abroad.

Keywords

English, proficiency, perception, competence, academic staff, higher education, Kosovo

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Introduction

“English, the global language.” - The statement people articulate every day.

In recent years, the English language is something you hear from politicians all across the world, say on the news. English advertising and billboards can be found almost everywhere. However, this does not mean that everyone knows how to speak English¹. There are also countries around the world that do not recognize English as a global language. Though, what makes English a global language? Firstly, a language can be proclaimed as the dominant language of a country, allowing it to be used as a communication medium in areas such as politics, the judiciary, the press, and academia, and frequently, that language is referred to as a ‘second language’. Secondly, even if a language seems to have no formal position, it can also be prioritized in a country’s foreign-language teaching. Global academies as well as commercial communities recognize the need for a global language, and it is here that perhaps the acceptance of a common global language is most evident, both in lecture halls, and conference rooms, and also in the hundreds of individual connections made every day all over the world. What makes it special, is that when it comes to education, English, as a lingua franca, will give us access to knowledge, and having to learn, as well as utilizing English will not only provide us with a somewhat unifying thread, but will also introduce us to the fascinating world of ideas².

As mentioned above, the era in which we find ourselves now is unanimously associated with globalization, where the need for a common language is felt more deeply and strongly than before. Clearly, that language is none other than English, with an unprecedented extension worldwide and in many domains. English does the job of bridging people with whom they have nothing in common. Out of the domains where English is widely spoken, it is certainly in the sector of higher education. In this context, English has been the language of Higher Education Institutions (HEI), in particular in those universities that are directed abroad for the establishment of international relations³. Of course, many higher education institutions, also through the effects of the faster process of internationalization, have assumed many strategies to meet the demands of the internationalization of higher education, which is described as “the process of integrating an international/intercultural dimension into teaching, research, and service functions of the institution.” The most notable strategy pursued by universities to achieve ‘Internationalization’ was to change English as the language of instruction, either fully or partially on campus⁴.

The pressure on universities to improve their global profile in the competitive higher education sector has made internationalization more important for higher education institutions today. Universities look beyond national borders. University councils set goals and devise strategies for internationalization. Some of these strategies have been agreed upon at the national and international levels, such as the Bologna Declaration of 1999⁵⁻⁸. Since Bologna, the 29 signatory states have been implementing the Bachelor-Master-Doctorate

structure and are implementing other instruments (ECTS (European Credit Transfer System) credits, diploma supplements, etc.) that are intended to pave the way for higher education. In addition, a European Higher Education Area has been created that is internationally competitive and attracts students from inside and outside Europe.

These trends highlight the issue of the European language and the challenges of communication in a multilingual environment. They force European higher education politicians to face the language issue and think about converting their curricula from the national language to the international standard - the English language. However, this process is not without its problems, especially since lecturers may have language restrictions. There may also be obstacles at other levels due to the cultural and political sensitivity of the issue. For example, policymakers at the local level may feel that the switch to English will come at the expense of the local language and teaching traditions, or there may even be legal restrictions on adopting such a policy⁹.

Not only is the Bologna Process seen as vital in the internationalization process, but Erasmus as well. ERASMUS (European Region Action Scheme for the Mobility of University Students) was founded in 1987 with main goals such as training youth, supporting personal and professional development of students in education, in Europe and other countries elsewhere. Erasmus+ has played a pivotal part in a more comprehensive and deliberate approach to the internationalization process of higher education institutions in Europe, and has served as a model for universities, countries, and regions around the world. The impact is quite extensive, or more likely to say Erasmus+ in the 1980s was the catalyst for a more deliberate approach to the internationalization of higher education institutions. Erasmus+ laid the groundwork for the Bologna Process’ inception and built mechanisms to facilitate it, such as the European Credit Transfer System (ECTS)¹⁰. When it comes to mobility, the hub is usually focused on students. While many higher education institutions in Europe have procedures in place to increase student exchanges, there is seldom a deliberate effort to encourage staff mobility, despite the fact that the Erasmus+ program provides financing for academics including administrative personnel¹¹. A much more systematic approach to academic mobility has obvious benefits in terms of improving research, and education, as well as overall professional growth¹². Lecturers are critical to any educational institution’s global expansion¹³.

The Bologna Process and the HEIs have faced the issue of quality assurance, and there has also been a greater emphasis on the globalization of quality assurance, as well as how national mechanisms in Europe collaborate to produce common criteria and generally recognize their certification judgments. Accreditation departments are expected to look into the advancements and identify the most complicated matters associated with them as the HE (Higher Education) ideology is progressively globalized and cross-border proposals such as franchises, campuses, correspondence courses, joint and dual

degree programs influence accreditation and quality assurance. Clearly, the internationalization process of higher education in Europe appears bright, but its influence will only be realized if different stakeholders and partners in this ongoing transition process embrace a new discussion regarding justifications, advantages, resources, possibilities, and challenges¹⁴.

Limitations and statement of the study

This study has to be considered in light of some limitations. The questionnaire was sent via email to each lecturer from October 2024 to December 2024. It covers the public universities of Kosovo where the absolute number of the lecturers participating was 336. Of the participating lecturers, 55.4% were male, and 44.6% were female. The objectives of this study were to identify the mastery of the English language among the academic staff of the Public Universities of Kosovo. As the importance of the English language is defined as a key for better university campus work, where does the academic staff stand with their English language level, what do they think about the use of the English language when their mother tongue is not helpful enough during their lectures or campus work, did the lack of the English language proficiency has set back or slowed their academic work, and how do they evaluate the importance of the English language in the universities?

Research questions

The study is guided by the following questions:

1. How do lecturers perceive their English language proficiency and competence?
2. Is English language proficiency seen as crucial for their work?

Literature review

Known as the Latin of the 21st century, the English language is now playing the most powerful function in the internationalization of higher education. On a global scale, the English language is used mainly by 53 percent of the professionals in the CAP (Changing Academic Profession) survey; 17 percent use it as their native language and 36 percent use it as their second or third language¹⁴. Despite the fact that 51 percent of academics use English as a lingua franca for research purposes rather than teaching purposes, only 30 percent use it for teaching. This disparity mostly affects non-native speakers. Almost all academics who are native English speakers utilize English for both teaching and research. While the use of the English language as a foreign language is a strong sign of the internationalization process of the universities in countries where English is not a dominant language, the link between the usage of the English language and the internationalization process of university is less evident in English-speaking nations. Academic institutions and professors in these nations have an advantage since practically all of them or most of the academics speak English. However, the usage of the English language as a language cannot be regarded as an indicator of engagement in worldwide research networks. Furthermore, the usage of the English language relates to academics and their contributions to the internationalization process of their higher education¹⁴.

Today, internationalization and globalization have a significant influence on higher education. This is because higher education is both an actor and a reactor in these processes. It is an actor in the sense that it is the agent of internationalization and globalization, and a reactor in the sense that it responds to the effects of internationalization and globalization. Regarding higher education, internationalization of higher education can be defined as the process of integration into the international/intercultural dimension in the teaching, research, and Institutional service functions¹⁵.

If we look at universities more at the local level, it is found that, despite global pressure, reactions depend on their past and history^{16,17}. Although internationalization is considered an indicator of success, a university will thrive once it has developed strong connections with local partners and agencies. This global-local dialectic becomes evident when we look at universities, which are global institutions rooted in local traditions and networks. Universities that have become entrepreneurial organizations have also been researched¹⁸. They are characterized by a strong core of leadership; a periphery of development; a diversified financing base; a strong academic heart, and strong incentives for internationalization and transfer.

Universities may be right in their concerns about students' English ability. But what about the English abilities of faculty members? Do universities require them to demonstrate their English proficiency to determine if they are competent in teaching in English? At the time, a policy or practice did not appear to be under consideration in HE, at least in the form of a written or official declaration in white papers¹⁹. Because there are no clear-cut, stated or unwritten standards regarding lecturers' English skills for employment, there is relatively little information in the literature on professors' attitudes toward their English skills and practices.

EMI (English Medium Instruction) describes the utilization of English to teach a non-linguistic course in a culture where English is not the dominant language and it has become one of the most significant trends confronting HEI in such situations today. The first wave of growth occurred in Europe, where most of the EMI study was undertaken. In Europe, there were nearly 11 times more EMI programs in 2014 than in 2001²⁰. Linguistically, only a few academics have been involved in studies regarding the perceived English language competency of HE stakeholders and their use at EMI institutions. For example, in their study of the efficiency of the EMI policy in the Korean setting, discovered that instructors were dissatisfied with their English language abilities²¹. A group of non-native English lecturers reported a variety of issues with their language usage and abilities in a study²², which mostly covers problems linked to oral language output, such as pronunciation, accent, fluency, and intonation-related complaints. Similarly, the same issue was identified among 44 lecturers who were reported to have the most difficulty with pronunciation while teaching subject courses²³. It was discovered, however, that professors expressed a common concern about their language competence: being unable to cope with EMI linguistically at a desirable and desired level. Finally, in contrast, a research study

discovered that lecturers were satisfied with their English skills and gave favorable self-evaluations²⁴.

On the other hand, over 45 percent of the academic staff at Leiden and Delft Universities in the Netherlands have a level of proficiency at C1 or higher²⁵, and this level is the minimum requirement for the university to teach in English at more than half of the 70 European universities surveyed²⁶.

Internationalization of higher education institutions in the Western Balkans is largely considered as a tool for assisting national changes and strengthening productive capacities²⁷. Numerous international organizations, particularly the European Union, provide economic support to most internationalization activities. Because the nations and systems in the Western Balkans are so different, it is hard to make broad generalizations. Higher education institutions and study are still poorly funded in many nations, universities are losing their best academic staff and students, who have already gone abroad, and foundational reforms are hard to implement due to a lack of ideological freewill and weak governance at both the systemic and institutional levels. Transnational proposals, such as the Bologna Process Communiques, frequently result in very minor modifications in national systems. Cross-functional and cross-collaboration offer tremendous potential for the internationalization process. There are already a number of key programs in place to promote collaboration in academic programs. According to the results of one opinion poll, academics in the nation are ready to collaborate with partners from Western Balkan institutions. When asked if their institution should prioritize collaboration with universities or higher education institutions in the Western Balkans, academics from Kosovo (98.3%) and Albania (93.5%) agreed with this statement, whereas those from North Macedonia (77.6%) and Bosnia and Herzegovina (60%). The other four countries that disagreed with this statement are: Montenegro (44.3%), Serbia (27.5%), Croatia (26.2%), and Slovenia (20.4%). Individual countries hunt for partners and form connections in the burgeoning European Higher Education Arena based on a sense of proximity and a shared tradition that they want to preserve and enhance²⁷.

Ultimately, the purpose of English nowadays in higher education is becoming more essential every day²⁸.

Methodology of the study

Methodology background

The purpose of this case study was to explore the English language proficiency, perception and competence among the academic staff of Public Universities in Kosovo, the internationalization of higher education in Kosovo, and the development of the English language as a global language in public universities in Kosovo. The main aim of the study was to investigate the lecturers' English language proficiency, the function of the English language, and the potential problems the academic staff might face with their English language mastery. The current study adopts a quantitative and qualitative survey technique to analyze the perception of the lecturers of public universities in Kosovo, whether English language proficiency is seen as a

critical helper, if it has its good sides on campus-universities or not, and the effect of the English language in the internationalization process.

Participants

The data were collected in the setting of Kosovo Higher Education by surveying lecturers of the public universities of Kosovo. The participants were from the following universities: University "Hasan Prishtina" of Prishtina, University "Ukshin Hoti" of Prizren, University "Haxhi Zeka" of Peja, University "Kadri Zeka" of Gjilan, University "Isa Boletini" of Mitrovica, University "Fehmi Agani" of Gjakova, University of "Applied Sciences" of Ferizaj. Table 1 presents the demographic characteristics of the academic staff who participated in the study, including their gender, age group, and years of experience. The sampling of the research consisted of a total of 336 lecturers. The survey consisted of a group of Full Professors, Associate Professors, Assistant Professors, Lecturers, and Teaching Assistants, aged between 25 to 60. The questionnaire was designed and implemented through Google Forms and sent via email to each participant. All the participants signed a written consent form before answering the questions.

Research design

This study employs mixed methods for data collection and analysis. Quantitative methods such as survey research design (including the answered questions shown in pie charts by percentage), and qualitative methods (previous findings and studies from various authors and open-ended questions to achieve the aim of this study) based on data collection through questionnaires. The effectiveness of English language proficiency at the university level was assessed based on the perspectives of lecturers.

Instruments and data analysis

The questionnaire was only designed as a spreadsheet to collect data. The questionnaire consisted of 20 questions to test

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of participants.

		Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Female	150	44,6
	Male	186	55,4
Age	25-30	32	9,5
	30-39	85	25,3
	40-49	104	31,0
	50-59	86	25,6
	60+	29	8,6
Years of teaching	0-10	124	36,9
	11-20	133	39,6
	21+	79	23,5

the main objectives of the research, yes/no questions, multiple-choice questions, and open-ended answer questions. The results are displayed in pie charts, which consist of all questions and answers expressed as a percentage of the questionnaire, including two of the questions displayed as summary at the end of the results bearing in mind that they were open-ended questions. The survey on language perception and proficiency was conducted from October to December 2024. The results collected from the data show that the majority of the lecturers held a positive view of their English language proficiency and their English language usage in their academic work.

Results

The following table presents the summarized responses from the questionnaire conducted among academic staff in Kosovo's public universities regarding English language proficiency, perception, and competence.

Analysis of Results:

1. Mastery of English Language

As shown in [Table 2](#), the majority of respondents rated their English language proficiency as either 'good' or 'very good', particularly in reading and writing skills.

2. English Proficiency and Employment

A significant 61.3% of respondents stated that their English proficiency helped them secure their current academic positions. However, 38.7% reported that English proficiency was not a factor, possibly due to non-English course offerings or hiring policies at the time of their employment.

3. English as a Job Requirement

Only 38.4% reported that English proficiency was a formal requirement for their positions, while the majority (61.6%) indicated that it was not. This suggests that many

Table 2. Results excerpted from the questionnaire.

Question	Results
How well do you master the English language?	Good (39.2%), Very good (35.0%), Excellent (12.6%), Sufficient (9.9%), Poor (3.3%)
Has your English proficiency helped you land the job you currently have?	Yes (61.3%), No (38.7%)
Was English language competence a requirement for your job?	Yes (38.4%), No (61.6%)
I think knowledge of the English language is necessary for the job I do.	Agree (39.3%), Strongly agree (56.5%), Disagree (3.3%), Strongly disagree (0.9%)
Have you faced any situations when your lack of English proficiency was an obstacle for your work?	Yes (181), No (155)
I believe knowledge of the English language improves performance in other academic areas.	Strongly agree (62.8%), Agree (34.5%), Disagree (2.4%), Strongly disagree (0.3%)
My English proficiency has helped me in such cases as when particular materials in my mother tongue were hard or impossible to find.	Strongly agree (58.9%), Agree (37.2%), Disagree (3.6%), Strongly disagree (0.3%)
University staff must be proficient in another language other than their mother tongue.	Strongly agree (69.9%), Agree (30.1%), Disagree (0.3%)
How much does not knowing the English language hinder the development or implementation of key university components?	A little (5.7%), Considerable (38.1%), A lot (56.3%)
In which languages do you publish your scientific articles?	Albanian (16.7%), English (72.9%), German (2.1%), Albanian & English (2.7%), Turkish & English (1.5%), Albanian & German (0.6%), English & German (0.6%), Other (3.0%)
Technology requires some type of English proficiency.	Strongly agree (64.3%), Agree (33.0%), Disagree (2.7%)
Knowing English has helped me double my professional network, leading to additional opportunities.	Strongly agree (67.0%), Agree (29.2%), Disagree (3.9%)
Evaluate your English language abilities (1–10 scale).	1 (5), 2 (5), 3 (8), 4 (19), 5 (35), 6 (69), 7 (90), 8 (56), 9 (25), 10 (24)
How much do you believe the English language helps you in your academic staff? (1–10 scale).	1 (5), 2 (6), 3 (9), 4 (15), 5 (24), 6 (48), 7 (63), 8 (74), 9 (26), 10 (66)

universities historically did not mandate English proficiency for employment but may now recognize its growing importance.

4. English as a Necessity in Academic Work

Most respondents strongly agreed (56.5%) or agreed (39.3%) that English is essential for their work, highlighting its importance in academic settings. Only a small fraction disagreed (3.3%) or strongly disagreed (0.9%).

5. English Proficiency as an Obstacle

More than half of the participants (181) acknowledged that a lack of English proficiency had been an obstacle in their academic work, while 155 respondents stated otherwise. This finding underscores the challenges faced by some academic staff in engaging with international materials and collaborations.

6. English and Performance in Other Academic Areas

A strong majority (62.8%) strongly agreed, and 34.5% agreed that English proficiency positively impacts other academic areas. Only a small percentage (2.4%) disagreed, indicating a near-universal recognition of English as a beneficial skill.

7. English Proficiency and Access to Materials

Many respondents (58.9% strongly agreed, 37.2% agreed) reported that their English skills helped them access academic materials that were unavailable in their mother tongue, further emphasizing the practical advantages of English proficiency.

8. Foreign Language Proficiency for University Staff

An overwhelming 69.9% strongly agreed and 30.1% agreed that university staff should be proficient in a language other than their mother tongue. This demonstrates a broad consensus on the value of multilingualism in academia.

9. English and Internationalization

The lack of English proficiency was perceived as a significant barrier to internationalization, with 56.3% stating it hinders development “a lot” and 38.1% considering it a “considerable” issue. Only 5.7% believed it had little impact.

10. Languages Used for Scientific Publications

English dominated as the preferred language for publishing scientific articles (72.9%), followed by Albanian (16.7%). Other languages such as German, Turkish, and mixed-language publications accounted for minor proportions.

11. Technology and English Proficiency

The majority strongly agreed (64.3%) or agreed (33.0%) that English proficiency is essential for using technology in academic settings, reinforcing the language’s role in modern education.

12. English and Professional Networking

A significant proportion of lecturers (67.0% strongly agreed, 29.2% agreed) believed that English had helped expand their professional networks, leading to additional career opportunities.

13. Self-Evaluation of English Abilities

Responses varied widely on a scale from 1 to 10, with the highest concentration around levels 6 to 8, indicating a generally moderate to high level of proficiency among the respondents.

14. Perceived Importance of English in Academic Work

Similar to the self-evaluation question, most responses clustered around higher ratings, with many respondents ranking English as highly important (scores of 7–10), further reinforcing its significance in academia.

Open-ended questions - Summary section

The first one asked the lecturers, “Why is it important for you to improve your English language skills? (If you are already proficient, comment on why you think it is necessary for others to have some type of knowledge in another language.)”

As for the responses, they were quite impressive and the most key ones were:

“1. No serious research can be done without using international publications, and the main language of those publications is English; 2. Nowadays, being bilingual is very important because it helps in your work; 3. For communication, literature, and lectures; 4. Because the English language mastery gives you more opportunities for everything an intellectual person needs, especially the academic staff; 5. English is the main language in the world used in fields such as: science, technology, and business; 6. To have access to more innovative literature; 7. To increase the quality of teaching; 8. To publish scientific works in English without having to pay for translations; 9. All science is in English, so proficiency in English is essential; 10. Mastery of English is essential at this time so that you can be up to date with the information and changes that are happening in the field of study. Given the fact that all the publications are being published in the English language; 11. As a lecturer, you must speak English in order to be as close as possible to developed countries; 12. English is the *Lingua franca* today; 13. Since I do not know English well, I suffer the great consequences of not being able to speak with foreign colleagues; 14. Today everything is in English; even university documents are translated into English; 15. If I knew English well, I would have a higher position; 16. Improving English language skills is a big step for all university employees; 17. Because English language proficiency is as important as the doctoral degree; 18. Knowledge of English is something elementary; it is a passport for us; 19. Indeed, English is more valuable than other diplomas and certificates. We translate research works mainly through translators who lose their value and quality; 20. It is important to improve English language skills because of scientific studies and international mobility; 21. It is seen as a helper for the lecturers’ careers; a supreme helper for presentations, participation in conferences, scientific projects, and publications; 22. The lecturers must improve their English skills so that they can have access to materials that are not translated into their mother tongue, but only in English; 23. The mastery of the English language is valuable because nowadays, all of the scientific articles are

published in English, and the English language proficiency leads us to professional development and improves our academic performances.”

And the second question was, “Because university staff continuously work with international institutions, does English language proficiency play a role in quality communication between the two?” The most key answers were:

“1. The main role, the better the communication, the more influential in fulfilling the requirements for reciprocity between institutions; 2. Increasing the quality of cooperation; 3. Development, quality improvement, exchange of experiences and knowledge; 4. An extremely important place in developing various areas of the University; 5. There is no quality communication without knowing English very well, and there is no international cooperation without mastering the English language; 6. The reputation of the university is different if there is quality communication; 7. Without communication, there is no cooperation, precisely in English, meetings with international colleagues take place mainly; 8. With quality communication we show our values as wise and hardworking people; 9. Applications, for example, for Erasmus+, Heras+, Horizon2020, are done in English; 10. English language proficiency plays an incomparable position in international collaborations and strengthens the reports of these international collaborations; most importantly, it plays a key role in the exchange of academic experiences with various universities around the world.”

Discussion

The findings reveal that participants in this survey considered their English language mastery to be at a medium level, with 65% rating their overall academic English as “good.” This finding provides counter-evidence to 29 where Japanese lecturers, under government initiatives, released a series of proposals to begin testing all four English language skills in university entrance examinations. These efforts were also intended to promote the use of English in higher education, enabling individual universities to select the most appropriate language requirements. The reforms emerged in response to evaluations indicating that Japanese university lecturers themselves demonstrated very low levels of English proficiency.

For the next three questions on English language acknowledgment and usage in the public universities of Kosovo, English language proficiency was seen as a helper to land academic jobs, but when it came to job requirements, most of the lecturers answered negatively, since the majority of the lecturers have been lecturing in universities for a long time now and English language was not a requirement back then, and as for being considered as a necessity, 4.2% of the participants claimed that they do not see the English language usage that way. Furthermore, it is claimed that hardly any of the interviewed lecturers from Austria, Italy, or Poland seemed to have a clear understanding of what an adequate English language level could be and that some assumed that their selection had been predicated on whether they would have a doctorate from an Anglophone country, taught abroad, or were simply thought

to speak English well by managers³⁰. A poll found that 83% of “informed observers” in 54 nations believed there were not enough competent lecturers in their country, even though the term “qualified” was left ambiguous, allowing it to be construed merely in terms of English language or qualification³¹. Finally, it is obvious from a variety of study sources that lecturers in many academic fields believe their topic is less dependent on language. Nonetheless, considering the absence of lecturer English proficiency, it is obvious that the great majority of respondents believe that a high level of English language proficiency is necessary³².

According to the participants’ answers to the next question, their response to the lack of English proficiency setting back the lecturers’ work can be seen as a demonstration of their English language proficiency lack in general, since the acknowledgment of the English language empowers the lecturers to set up a fruitful correspondence in their academic work. Inadequate resources certainly have an impact on the effectiveness of EMI policies^{33–36}, and the shortcomings appeared to harm professors in this study. The EMI program was introduced by different foreign universities where superior facilities were expected. Due to the lack of fundamental resources, lecturers were put under unexpected pressure to change their teaching materials and techniques. The Internet, for example, may provide a wealth of English teaching tools³⁷.

The results also point out that lecturers at public universities in Kosovo see the English language as a notable helper in cases when particular materials in the lecturers’ mother tongue were hard to find. However, it is pointed out that the Danish language may be threatened by the increasing use of English as the language of the lecturers’ publications, and if Danish “ends up losing its domains,” that is, once it is no longer used in premium domains such as higher education, it will lose value and lead to a less developed vocabulary, which leads to more use of English²⁴.

Corresponding to the following questions on the development of internationalization and the academic staff’s being proficient in another language other than their mother tongue, the lecturers voted positively on these two questions, claiming that they see the need for other languages proficiency since English language proficiency itself and components such as mobility of students and the academic staff, teaching quality, and so on, play a vital role in the development of internationalization. Equivalent to this, many European countries and systems remain committed to teaching in the national language including the developed policies to encourage the use of the national languages alongside English³⁸.

According to the results, most of the lecturers claimed that the language they use for their scientific articles is the English language, whereas the rest of them claimed that they also publish their work in Albanian, German, Turkish, Bosnian, and other different foreign languages. According to this, it is stated that even though *Principia Mathematica* of Newton’s was written in Latin, yet, nowadays scientific articles are published

mostly in English³⁹. A 2012 study published in the scientific journal *Research Trends* investigated publications gathered by Scopus, the world's biggest collection of peer-reviewed journals. To be eligible for inclusion in Scopus, a publication published in a language other than English should at the very least contain English abstracts. The study discovered that 80 percent of the more than 21,000 articles from 239 nations already in the database were written in English. The study focused on eight nations that generate a high number of scientific journals and discovered that the ratio of English to non-English articles had grown or stayed steady in all but one of them in the previous few years. Words such as oxygen or hydrogen sound like science. However, these terms originated from Russian, Greek, and French⁴⁰. Nowadays, though, even scientists and professors publish their work or their new discoveries in English. Some believe that Latin is the language of science, but when it comes to publications, they definitely use the English language.

Based on the findings, it is reasonable to say that the majority of lecturers from public universities in Kosovo rated their English language abilities in general as "good". In contrast, a large percentage of Turkey University lecturers evaluated their English positively and that more than 90 percent of those participating evaluated their English language level as "good"¹⁹. Several studies concur in emphasizing the relevance of teaching staff's linguistic and methodological expertise in ensuring the quality and proper execution of foreign programs. Furthermore, recent publications from several European authorities emphasize the importance of verifying these competencies⁴¹. However, there is no agreement among Spanish universities on what level of English is required to teach topics in that language. Majority of Spanish universities required a B2 level to allow lecturers to enrol in EMI programs; 28 percent required a C1, and 34 percent had no prerequisite at all⁴². Not only are there enormous differences across universities in terms of requirements, or absence thereof, as well as the level required, should that requirement exist, but there are also huge differences in the process of confirming²⁶.

After analyzing the effect of English language usage in public universities of Kosovo, the internationalization process, the English as a global language, all the results concluded that the utilization of the English language is seen as a dominant tool among the academic staff, that it presents higher education with opportunities and challenges, opportunities for developing education, and that it helps the academic staff get access to the world's diverse knowledge. The internationalization of higher education also encourages cultural interactions, knowledge exchanges, and research collaboration. At the same time, it fosters understanding, mutual dependence, and friendships among universities and institutions worldwide.

Conclusion

In this study, the researchers have focused on the functions of English language usage and the role of the English language in the internationalization process of higher education in Kosovo. The researchers discussed the concepts of internationalization and globalization, as well as their implications for higher education. They have also claimed the potential

and problems that Kosovo's public universities may face. In this paper, the researchers sought to demonstrate that the English language, as a prominent language of worldwide communication, plays a significant task in the internationalization of higher education in Kosovo. There is no doubt that lecturers of the public universities in Kosovo, believe they are capable of delivering their subject matter courses in English. This dispels doubts about lecturers' English language mastery because there is no publicly defined or implemented procedure for evaluating lecturers' English who want to work at EMI universities. As this study has revealed, the mandatory implementation of EMI without reference to instructors' language proficiency, the lack of a much-needed support structure and usable instructors to conduct EMI classes, and the voluntary implementation of EMI across academic fields have all resulted in several unintended consequences. Findings such as the ones presented in this study have significant significance for future EMI policy implementation at the public universities of Kosovo. Though the internationalization process poses challenges for Kosovo's higher education, it can be argued that the establishment of a transnational academic system in the form of joint programs provides excellent opportunities for the public universities of Kosovo to improve and update their curricula in the direction of standardization.

In conclusion, the internationalization of higher education in Kosovo, as well as the development of the English language as a global language, has created a need to reassess the role of English in the development of higher education in Kosovo.

Ethics and consent

This study was conducted in accordance with the principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki. Ethical approval for this research study was obtained from the Scientific Committee of the University "Ukshin Hoti" Prizren on 20.09.2024. All participants provided written informed consent prior to participation.

Data availability

All the data regarding this study can only be used by the researchers in accordance with the consent form signed by the participant prior to participation.

The data supporting this study are not publicly available due to ethical restrictions and participant confidentiality. Data access can be requested by contacting the lead author at sejdi.sejdiu@uni-prizren.com. Requests will be reviewed by the ethics committee at University "Ukshin Hoti" Prizren, and access may be granted under conditions that maintain participant confidentiality.

However, the extended data supporting the findings of this study, including the questionnaire and consent form, are openly available on Zenodo under a **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)** licence at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15828375>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16163429>⁴³

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Open Peer Review

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This article addresses a valuable topic in the Kosovo higher education. In fact, English language competence and improved internationalization may be one critical way out through a crisis of rapid decline in student numbers in Kosovo higher education institutions, which came as a result of recent demographic trends (steep decline in birth-rate and emigration of young people to western countries after recent EU visa liberalization).

The introduction offers a valuable contextualization of language competence and internationalization in Kosovo, the expansion of staff mobility opportunities, the growth of online learning, and the emergence of artificial intelligence. This section also successfully situates the study within relevant developments in higher education and the broader socio-educational context of Kosovo. The link between language competence and internationalization is appropriately highlighted.

Further below are presented key issues / comments that if adequately addressed would make this a notable scholarly contribution in the field.

Literature Review:

In several instances, in-text citations and quotations are not adequately integrated into the sentence structure – they should be introduced in a way that explicitly connects them to the argument being developed.

Methodology:

The study is referred to as a “case study,” yet the article does not provide sufficient evidence to substantiate this designation. The methodology section does not clearly define the object of the case study, nor does it outline additional methods (beyond the questionnaire) that would facilitate deeper analysis, triangulation, comparison, or verification of findings, common to case study research.

The research is presented as employing a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative and

qualitative elements. However, the qualitative component appears limited. In their methodology section, the authors identify two elements of qualitative research: (a) reviewing reports and (b) including two open-ended questions in the questionnaire. First, it is questionable whether the reading and analysis of reports, without systematic qualitative analysis, constitutes a qualitative research method. Second, in the absence of interviews or focus group discussions—commonly employed in qualitative research—two open-ended questions may not be sufficient to substantiate a robust qualitative component.

Even if the qualitative element were accepted as such, its presentation and analysis do not follow established qualitative analysis procedures (e.g., coding, identification of themes, categorization). Instead, the data are described rather than analyzed. This descriptive approach risks overlooking valuable insights that could have emerged from a thematic or category-based analysis.

Regarding sampling, the authors should clarify whether the number of respondents is sufficient to support the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, further statistical analyses (e.g., factor analysis, regression analysis) would enhance the validity and reliability of the research instruments and results.

Presentation and Analysis:

The presentation of findings would benefit from tabular or graphical representations, particularly those allowing cross-tabulations or correlations between variables such as respondents' institution, age, academic title, and field of study. Without such comparative analysis, potentially relevant patterns may remain undiscovered (for more on this see also the section of discussion below).

In discussing faculty perceptions of their English language competence, it is unclear whether "good" levels of competence are consistently interpreted by respondents. It would be important to know whether respondents were provided with standardized descriptors of language proficiency (e.g., CEFR levels) to ensure reliability. Without such reference points, deeper analysis or follow-up interviews would be necessary to determine what "good" or "very good" actually signifies for the participants, but also for analysis of results.

The authors could strengthen the analysis by comparing self-reported language competence data with results from other studies conducted in one or two higher education institutions in Kosovo.

Discussion of Results:

The discussion remains largely descriptive and does not fully engage in analytical interpretation of the findings. It would be beneficial to identify the key challenges faced by Kosovo's higher education faculty and institutions with regard to language competence, its use in professional practice, and its role in career development.

Analysis and Discussion:

The analysis of the results in this paper is presented mainly in a descriptive form, which makes the presentation of the data clear and easy to follow. However, the analysis remains descriptive and falls short of using more advanced statistical methods, which would enable the extraction of deeper connections between variables and a more meaningful interpretation of the phenomenon. The results remain separate from each other, without being linked between variables such as age, academic title or field of study, which leaves room for potential differences between groups to not be identified. The discussion of the results remains mainly descriptive, since the results are presented without being accompanied by a more in-depth theoretical interpretation or direct comparisons with the literature. The use of inferential analyses, such as correlation, linear regression, factor analysis or ANOVA, would have helped to discover the factors that have the

most influence and to build more reliable statistical connections. Also, comparing groups by academic title, experience, or field of study would have provided a more complete and understandable overview of the phenomenon studied. Including these elements would deepen the interpretation, increase the reliability of the findings, and contribute to a clearer positioning of the study within the existing scientific literature.

Conclusions and Recommendations:

This section requires greater alignment with the study's findings. At present, English Medium Instruction (EMI) appears to resurface from the introduction and literature review rather than as a conclusion logically derived from the analysis. A more coherent link between the results, discussion, and conclusions is necessary.

Language and Style:

The article would benefit from a thorough linguistic revision to address typographical errors, improve vocabulary precision, and enhance syntactic clarity. A version of the article with this reviewer's more concrete suggested edits is available.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it engage with the current literature?

Partly

Is the study design appropriate and is the work technically sound?

Partly

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Partly

Are all the source data and materials underlying the results available?

Partly

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

No

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: I, Xhavit Rexhaj, and my colleague Fidan Qerimi, are engaged in applied linguistics research using both qualitative and quantitative methods and instrument. We do not have any limitations to review this article.

We confirm that we have read this submission and believe that we have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however we have significant reservations, as outlined above.

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.21589.r57886>

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Nuhi Bllaca

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The study aimed to explore English language proficiency, perceptions, and competence among academic staff at public universities in Kosovo. Data were gathered from 366 participants across seven public universities in Kosovo. The paper makes a valuable contribution by addressing a gap in the literature on the role of English in the internationalization of higher education and its use as a medium of instruction (EMI). This is particularly significant in the Kosovar context, where no previous study has investigated this topic. The study also generated important findings regarding academic staff's self-reported English proficiency and their views on the importance of English for academic work, research, and publication.

However, before indexing, several improvements could strengthen quality of the paper:

Introduction:

The authors should clearly introduce the aims of the study in the first section (Introduction) and explicitly articulate the research gap relevant to the study's purpose. They should also provide a clear statement on the expected contribution of the paper, particularly in the Kosovar context.

Literature Review:

Some of the research questions currently included in the Introduction should be moved to the Literature Review. In addition, the authors should incorporate more studies aligned with the topic or, where such studies are lacking, emphasize this absence. This would allow them to better highlight the research gap addressed by their study.

Methodology:

While the study uses a questionnaire, there is insufficient detail about its validity and reliability. The authors should provide more information about the design, piloting, and implementation of the questionnaire in order to assure readers of the robustness of the data-gathering instrument.

Proofreading:

The paper would benefit from careful proofreading to avoid minor inconsistencies or wording that could confuse readers.

Minor Issues:

A number of small issues have already been flagged in the text through comments and should be addressed prior to indexing.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it engage with the current literature?

Yes

Is the study design appropriate and is the work technically sound?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Partly

Are all the source data and materials underlying the results available?

No

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: English for academic purposes; Peer interaction, Collaborative Writing; English language teaching both at pre-university and university contexts. Computer-mediated communications. Computer-assisted language learning. Task-based language teaching, etc.

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.
